

To Determine the Sensitivity & Specificity of Quinacrine Dihydrochloride Stain For Gender Determination By F Body Present in Human Pulp Tissue

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Abstract:

Y chromosome contains F-bodies. These F-bodies can be used to identify sex. The F-Body is typically described as a single fluorescent spot, approximately 0.25 um in diameter and of variable length, located halfway between the periphery and center of the nucleus. Y chromosome can be studied in the cells during interphase by staining with Quinacrine mustard when Y chromosome will fluoresce more brightly and its presence conclusively indicates the Y chromosome and sex in positive cases is invariably male.

Key Word: Quinacrine dihydrochloride, F body, pulp

Introduction:

Dental remains as teeth are an excellent material in living and nonliving populations for anthropological, genetic, odontologic and forensic investigations being hardest and chemically the most stable tissue in the body, they are selectively preserved and fossilized, thereby providing for the best records for evolutionary change. Their durability in the face of fire and bacterial decomposition makes them invaluable for identification.¹

The present study uses the tooth pulp tissue from extracted human teeth as the substratum for sexual characterization. The first reason to select the pulp as the preferred tissue for this study is its sequestered location. Embedded in a chamber surrounded by intact highly mineralized dentin and enamel, the pulp is vulnerable to the external environment only at a small apical aperture. Hence, the present study is designed to expand current knowledge on the constraints pertaining to sex discrimination in pulp tissue.

Source of data: The study sample consisted of 120 extracted teeth from patients (maxillary and mandibular combined) which were collected from the Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery of Career Post Graduate Institute of Dental Sciences & Hospital Lucknow.

Methodology:

Sample For The F-body Test:

- Of the 120 teeth taken for the study, 60 were taken from male subjects (group a) and 60 were taken from female subjects (group b).

- Pulp was obtained from groups a & b and each pulp smear were stained for F Body test by Quinacrine dihydrochloride (0.5%) dye.
- Individual tooth sample were microscopically examined from the groups in the present study.
- Tooth were extracted by method described by KRUGER.

For F-body test: -

Sectioning of the teeth:

- The tooth to be sectioned was embedded on modeling wax block
- To free the pulp, the crown was separated longitudinally by using a carborundum disc at 30,000 rpm. Similarly the root was split for pulp removal
- The whole of the pulp tissue was separated out of the pulp cavity, with the help of broach and forceps and transferred to a Eppendorf tube containing normal saline.
- It was then adequately washed in normal saline to remove any debris.

Fig 1: Sectioned Tooth

Obtaining clear suspension of pulp cells:

- a) The pulp tissue was transferred to a dry and clear centrifuge tubes and 0.5 ml of fixative (20% acetic acid) was used to soften the dental pulp.
- b) It was then crushed / teased with the glass rod sufficiently to isolate the pulp cells.
- c) Again 2ml of fixative(20%acetic acid) was added and the suspension is stirred well.
- d) A suspension thus obtained was centrifuged for 10 min at 1000 rpm.
- e) The supernatant was discarded leaving behind the pellet in the centrifuge tube.
- f) 2ml. of fresh fixative was then added to re-suspend the pellet and the process was repeated till a clear suspension of the pulp cell was obtained.

Fig: 2 Retrieved Pulp

Preparation of smear:

These smears were prepared on chilled glass slide by the air-drying method i.e., by dropping 2-3 drops of the clear suspension of the pulp cells on the slide from a distance of few inches, to obtain a monolayer of cells one smears was made from suspension of the specimen.

Fixing and Staining of the pulp smear staining with Quinacrine dihydrochloride:

- a) After drying at room temperature, a few drops of methanol were added to fix the material.
- b) After natural evaporation of methanol, the material was stained with 0.5% Quinacrine dihydrochloride for 20 minutes
- c) The slide was then washed with double distilled water and kept in Mellvaine's buffer (0.1 M citric acid, 0.2M Bi basic sodium phosphate) with pH of 5.5 for 3 minutes.
- d) The slide was then be washed with 0.4g/L magnesium chloride for 10 minutes and then a drop of Glycerol was added for mounting.
- e) A cover slip was placed on the top, avoiding trapping of any air bubbles.

Fig: 3 Quinacrine Dihydrochloride Stained Cells [Positive For F Body] 40x

Specimen observation:

F Body were observed under high power lens (40x) of fluorescent microscope in dark field having blue glass as excitation filter and orange glass as barrier filter. Only those cells which contained the characteristic Y chromatin i.e., a brightly fluorescent spot (F body) close to the nuclear membrane will be counted as positive.

Inclusion Criteria

- Subject who was active for prophylactic removable of asymptomatic tooth/teeth which would either Periodontally Compromised, Impacted, Indicated for extraction as a part of orthodontic treatment and subject with healthy mucosa.

Exclusion Criteria

- Subjects with any clinical sign/symptoms of any obvious pathology associated with the concerned tooth/ teeth and oral mucosa.

Result:

Corelation	Male	Female
Positive	46	1
Negative	14	59
Fisher's Exact Test P Value	<0.0001*	

*p-value significant

Table 1: Overall Gender Comparison of Q.S. for F-Body

Table 1 shows overall gender comparison of Q.S. for F-body. 46 males had positive and 14 males had negative Q.S. value for F-body, whereas 59 out of 60 females had negative values. Fisher's Exact Test P Value is <0.0001 showing p-value of less than 0.05. Thus, a statistically significant values positive Q.S. for F-body towards male and a negative correlation with female gender is seen.

Q.S. for F-body	Gender Prediction	
	Male	Female
Positive	46	14
Negative	1	59
Sensitivity (%)	97.87%	
Specificity (%)	80.82%	
Positive Predictive Value (%)	76.67%	
Negative Predictive Value (%)	98.33%	

Table 2: Sensitivity & specificity for Q.S. for F-body in gender prediction

Table 2 shows sensitivity of 97.87 %, specificity of 80.82%, Positive Predictive Value 76.67% and Negative Predictive Value 98.33% for Q.S. for F-body in gender prediction.

Discussion:

Y chromosome contains F-bodies. These F-bodies can be used to identify sex. Various studies have been under taken to identify F-bodies from pulpal tissue. Caspersson Tet al. (1970)² suggested that F-bodies can be applicable in forensic for sex determination. Dried blood stains, saliva, hair, and extracted dental pulp can serve as a sample for the test.

Bobrow and Vosa used quinacrine dihydrochloride (Atebrin) to demonstrate the Y chromosome in the interphase nuclei as a characteristic fluorescent body; thus, providing the ideal counterpart of the BB or X chromosome.³ Pearson PL et al. (1970)³ reported the fluorescent staining property of Y-chromatin in the nuclei of buccal mucosal cells, lymphocytes and fibroblasts and they found that the distal portion of the long arm of Y-chromosome fluoresced so intensely that it was easily recognized in both inter phase and mitotic nuclei as a distinctive fluorescent structure or F body Hence, the same material Quinacrine stain was used in our study to determine the F body.

Zech described a simple technique to demonstrate the Y chromosome using the quinacrine mustard.⁴ The alkylating agent such as quinacrine, accumulate in DNA regions rich in guanine and is responsible for the bright fluore scence of the Y chromosome. Seno M et al. (1973)⁵ carried out the detection of Y chromosome in the nuclei of dental pulp. They found that F body positive rate in the nucleated cells of male dental pulp was over 30%, even with the male teeth as old as 5 months, after the extraction. With female teeth, typical F body can not be detected, and F-body like spot has been observed in 0.4% of cells, indicating that there can be no error in the identification of male tooth from that of female one, even such an F body like spot is taken as an F-body itself.

In Table 1 the results showed that the overall gender comparison revealed a statistically significant values positive Q.S. for F-body towards male and a negative correlation with female gender. Fisher's extract test statistics showed p-value < 0.05.

Table 2 shows sensitivity of 97.87 % and specificity of 80.82% % for Q.S. for F-body in gender prediction. In the present study it was observed that there was sensitivity of 97.87 %, specificity of 80.82%, Positive Predictive Value 76.67% and Negative Predictive Value 98.33% for Q.S. for F-body in gender prediction with Fisher's exact test p value <0.0001 (significant) (Table 2).

In another study done by Khorate MM et al. (2014)⁴ who determined the diagnostic performance of X (Barr body [BB]) and Y(F body [FB]) chromosomes observed in dental pulp tissue for gender determination of an individual. They showed that the percentage of FB was in the range of 0-8 with mean to be 2.56 ± 2.31 . In males, the mean percentage of FB was found to be 59.8 ± 6.06 in the freshly extracted teeth.

Conclusion:

F-body recognition, is an highly effective method as a means of sex determination by tooth pulpal tissue.

Quinacrine dihydrochloride is very satisfactory for qualitative study, involving the differentiation of chromosomes and the visualization of Y chromatin.

References:

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